

Primer: Long-term Archiving of Experimental Data

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Making research data available to others for reuse is essential to scientific progress and the main purpose of archiving open research data (ORD). This is recognized in the [funding regulations](#) of the Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF), which requires grantees to archive the data in scientific repositories. The data should be made available as soon as possible and using repositories that enable making the data FAIR: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable ([Wilkinson et al., 2016](#)). This primer gives an overview of the types of data archives, what should be archived and the basic steps for a good archive. We also provide an example from archiving a cognitive neuroscience experiment.

Types of data archives

We can broadly classify the archives by how frequently we expect the data in them to be accessed. Table 1 summarizes different ‘temperatures’ of the data defined by access frequency ([Pernet et al., 2023](#)). Irrespective of the *temperature*, any data archiving should comply with the pertinent legal governance requirements. The contents and steps described in this primer can apply to any type of archive, but the presented use-case fits into the warm archive category. It should be noted that an archive does not necessarily make data publicly available immediately and most repositories allow restricting access, for example by requiring an application or applying an embargo until a publication is released.

Feature / Archive	Cold	Warm	Hot
Access frequency	Very low	Regular	Constant
Back-ups	No	Yes	Yes
Costs	Cheap	Expensive	Expensive
Content (data)	All	High-utility	High-utility
Costs	Cheap	Expensive	Expensive
Duration	Long	Long	Short/Medium
Medium	Tape	Disk/Server/Cloud	Disk/Server/Cloud
Online	No	Yes	Yes

Table 1: An overview of different types of data archives depending on the frequency of access.

- *Cold* data are not expected to be accessed in a long time but they should still be curated, unlike data considered *disposable* ([Pernet et al., 2023](#)). In some contexts, rarely accessed data can be essential. Collecting new data is usually much more expensive than archiving existing data, so it is generally advisable to cold-archive everything by default ([Pernet et al., 2023](#)). Tapes are relatively cheap and robust to data quality deterioration if stored in facilities that ensure data integrity preservation. Cold data tends to involve larger storage volume than warm and hot data, as it includes all data, including that of limited utility. Therefore it is often not cost-effective to make cold data available online.
- *Warm* data are expected to be accessed regularly and they are long-term archived in online servers or cloud repositories. Usually there are multiple back-up copies in physically separated locations to protect data integrity. Warm data are considered of high-utility for research reuse.
- *Hot* data are accessed constantly for a specific period of time, for example, while a project is running to share it with collaborators. Hot data are stored in relatively expensive online servers or cloud repositories, and are more likely to move location than cold and warm data.

What should I archive?

A data dump without the context provided by documentation and metadata has little scientific value. Thus, a data archive should have the following contents at a minimum:

a. Data

All collected or generated data usually undergoes some transformations before it can be interpreted or used in an analysis. Table 2 summarizes the differences between source, raw and derivative data. Any change between those categories, i.e., any transformation to the data should be transparent. The source vs raw distinction depends on the complexity of the data and may not always be necessary. An archive for a dataset publication usually has only source or raw data, while an archive associated with a research article should include derivatives involved in the analyses.

Data	Description
Source	Data as-collected, before any reconstruction or format conversion.
Raw	Unedited data or minimally changed (e.g., after a file format conversion).
Derivatives	Transformed or preprocessed data (e.g., filters, corrections, etc). Large data volume when files are saved at multiple processing stages.

Table 2: Different categories of data.

b. Metadata

Metadata are data about data which are intended for humans (documentation), or for both humans and machines (tables and metadata companion files). By machine-readable, we refer to those metadata that can be easily processed by computers without human intervention. The minimum of metadata to make data reusable in most projects is summarized in Table 3.

Metadata type	Description
Documentation*	Documents describing the project (goals, funding, license), filenaming convention, folder structure and procedures. README files with high-level folder content descriptions. Markdown format is recommended for simplicity and interoperability.
Tables**	Recording parameters, subjects, data provenance, etc. Require a code book of variable names. Comma-separated value (CSV) format is recommended for interoperability.
Companion files**	Structured metadata files stored adjacent to the data files with information such as that in the tables or more detailed. JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) format recommended for simplicity.

Table 3: Minimum set of metadata. * Human-readable; ** Human and machine-readable.

c. Code

A data archive should include any code relevant to its production, curation or reuse. This includes any script used to transform source into raw data or to generate any metadata files. More specific to experimental studies, any code to generate the stimuli and run the experiment needs to be provided. At a minimum, versions and dependencies of the software used to run this code need to be documented. Ideally, an archive would include an executable package of code with all dependencies needed to run it, although this requires more advanced efforts (see an overview in our primer on software containers for computational reproducibility, [Fraga Gonzalez et al., 2024](#)). Metadata on the hardware on which the experimental code was run are also important. For example, the monitor refresh rate or the sound card sampling rate can be crucial information when running time-sensitive experiments.

How do you prepare a data archive?

Step 1. Describe the project and data

Provide a brief description of the project goals, funding and license for reuse of data, as well as a description of the data types and volumes involved. This will help preparing the archive and estimating the storage resources that it may need. This information will be required by many repositories before submitting the data.

Step 2. Curate content and organize the project folders

This is better done from the beginning of the project as curating data after it has been collected will take more time and effort. It is recommended to follow existing standards that define folder structure, file naming conventions and relevant content of the metadata files. A systematic search for metadata standards is possible on [fairsharing](#), an extensive list kept up-to-date by different research communities ([Sansone et al., 2019](#)). If necessary, a standard can be adapted to the individual needs, although this is preferably done collaboratively. Some popular and growing standards like the Brain Imaging Data Structure ([BIDS](#), [Gorgolewski et al., 2016](#)) allow collaborative extension proposals. Irrespective of the standard used, the most important elements in a project folder organization are:

- The source and raw data folders should be kept in a location clearly independent and separated from the processed data.
- Not everything in a project folder might be suited for archiving. Sensitive data or data that will not be archived should be in a clearly identifiable location, preferably at the root level.
- The code should be located in a folder separate from the data and the analysis outputs. This folder is preferably synchronized with a version control system like Git ¹.
- There should be a balance between making folder names informative and keeping them concise. The full path to a file should not exceed the character limits of most operating systems, ranging from 255 to 260. Special characters are also not recommended (see our primer on file-naming conventions; [van de Wiel et al., 2023](#)).

Step 3. Find a target ORD repository

ORD repositories aim at preserving and making data freely accessible to anyone, promoting transparency and scientific collaboration. A key requirement for a repository is that it should provide a persistent identifier linking to the data and metadata. This, and how well it facilitates making the archived data FAIR are determining factors when judging the relevance of an ORD repository. The registry of research data repositories [re3data](#) ([Pampel et al., 2013](#)) allows the exploration of available repository by subject, content type and country. It also allows filtering based on features like versioning, metadata standards, data licenses and many others. The registry is also listed on the [SNSF website](#), which also gathers links to a few relevant institutional, generalist and discipline-specific repositories.

Data management plans

A great facilitator in the archiving process is a [Data Management Plan](#) (DMP), which is required for SNSF-funded projects. The DMP outlines the data life cycle, including where and how they will be shared and preserved. Having a DMP will help going through the steps described above before the start of the project. The SNSF website provides [guidelines](#) on how to structure the content of a DMP. There are also [examples of DMPs](#) on the website of the University Library Bern, and several online tools with templates, like [dmponline.dcc.ac.uk](#) and [argos.openaire.eu](#).

¹[Git](#) is a system to track changes in files that has become the *de facto* standard for version control for code.

A use-case from a cognitive neuroscience experiment

We present the case of a study using electroencephalography and an auditory experiment. The study is a simple experiment with few participants, however the data is relatively complex.

1. Project and data description

This single-center project from the field of neurolinguistics investigates brain activity in 15 healthy adults in the context of comprehension of speech in acoustically challenging circumstances. It is considered a pilot and proof concept study for future neurofeedback experiments. The study is part of a project funded by the SNSF, grant number PP00P1_163726 awarded to Prof. Dr. Alexis Hervais-Adelman (Department of Psychology, University of Zurich; Department of Basic Neuroscience, University of Geneva). The following data will be archived².

- **Tabular data.** The *participant information table* is a single file with data gathered from a questionnaire with demographic, language and hearing related items, as well as free text with lab notes taken by researchers during the recordings. The data was collected and stored with the web application [REDcap](#) where any identifying information (in this case date of birth) was masked before downloading the CSV file that will be archived. The *experiment performance tables* are multiple log CSV files generated by the experiment software and containing performance in separate files for each subject. In total, all tabular data is < 10 MB per subject.
- **Multi-channel electrophysiological time series.** *Electroencephalography* (EEG) data from 64 scalp electrodes recorded electrophysiological activity while subjects were at rest and while they performed an experimental task. 4 Additional electrodes recorded ocular movements and the signal of the audio presented in the task was added as an additional channel in the recordings. The sampling frequency was 2048 data points per second. The source file sizes amount to between 1.6 and 2.00 GB per participant, but they require some minimal preprocessing before further use which results in additional 2-2.5 GB per participant.
- **Stimuli (audio files).** In the experiment, participants had to listen to sentences and identify target words within them after each trial. The audio was manipulated to have different levels of degradation and background noise. The stimuli used in the task and the scripts to generate it and to present it to the participants are also archived. The folder with the manipulated audio files that were presented in the experiment is ~680 MB and the folder with the original raw audio and all steps of audio manipulations is approximately 3.86 GB.
- **Metadata.** Textual (TXT, MD, JSON) and tabular (CSV) information. JSON files are stored in the same location as the data files they accompanied. These files are around 500 KB altogether.

²Note: an online repository may ask for an exact account of the size and number of files submitted. For brevity, we report here only estimates.

2. Project folder contents and organization

The schematic in Figure 1 shows an overview of the project folder down to the second level subfolders. The project structure and metadata for the data folders was heavily based on the [BIDS](#) (Brain Imaging Data Structure) standards (data subfolders are not shown in this schematic for the sake of brevity).

3. Target repository

In this use case the plan is to archive the data in the repository from [SWISSUbase](#), which is an on-line platform based in Switzerland and operated by a consortium consisting of FORS (Swiss Centre of Expertise for the Social Sciences) and the Universities of Lausanne, Neuchâtel and Zurich. The repository is selected because it is a trusted repository that enables FAIR data archiving, it stores the data on servers in Switzerland, and it has a dedicated repository for linguistics research.

Figure 1: Folder organization in a cognitive neuroscience experiment.

Summary

Archiving data is a crucial part of any scientific project and researchers are increasingly expected to put their research data into online repositories. Our main recommendation for proper and affordable archiving is to plan it as early as possible and to organize a project with the archiving goal in mind. Curating a minimum set of metadata and documentation to avoid data dumps is an essential activity that can be integrated in the routine workflow of the research. These efforts will benefit the scientific community by preventing data dumps and research waste, and researchers themselves, as they contribute to more efficient and reproducible workflows.

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